

BUDDHISM PRINCIPLES IN SUICIDE PREVENTION

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Abstract

In the COVID 19 epidemic, almost every Human Being on Earth is suffering from some other mental health problem whether it is due to Economical crises, loss of a job, domestic violence, someone close that is infected by Coronavirus, or the recent death of loved ones due to Corona Virus. The pain of the loss of attachment or incapability to fulfill the hopes and desires of self or others leads to suicidal thoughts and self-destruction tendencies. It is documented by the Four Noble Truths that self-destruction is a type of experience that starts by wanting/sticking. neither we can escape from the “chakra of suffering” nor the suffering of suicide. This review article will also look at the psychosocial factors precipitating suicidal tendencies and the relative literature regarding the prevention of the same. Several researchers have indicated the Buddhism principle on general aspects such as only four noble truths, concentration, and/or meditation. From the present study, the Buddhist principles are divided into the following areas: 1) Buddhism toward suicide, 2) The suffering in suicide, 3) Detachment from Clinging, 4) Four noble truths, 5) Eightfold paths in the prevention of Suicide, 6) Role of concentration in the abandonment of Suicidal thoughts, 7) Practice of meditation and mindfulness, 8) Psychological and Sociological cause behind suicide.

Keywords: *Eightfold path, Suffering, Clinging, Four Noble Truths, Meditation, Concentration, Mindfulness.*

Introduction

Over 70% of the therapists who participated in the study reported an increase in the number of people who expressed a death wish or suicidal ideation after the outbreak of COVID-19. Although

most therapists capped the spike in suicide ideation at less than 10%, some thought that it could be up to 50%.

About two-thirds of physicians agree that the number of self-injurers has increased. While 29% responded positively, 36% thought it was possible. About 60% of the participants also witnessed increasing rates of relapse amongst people who had previously recovered or were recovering from mental health-related issues. (WHO, 2016)

Joseph in his study found that Anxiety (88.7%), job loss (76.1%), stress (73.6%), loneliness (73%), and financial insecurity (73%) were the top reasons for mental distress in people seeking help. “Anxiety levels are very high in most cases. Although usually not directly related to the virus, other problems have increased during this time. This has led to a feeling of overwhelm and, therefore, suicidal ideation,” June Thomas, a Bangalore-based counselor. (Joseph, 2020)

According to World Health Organization (WHO) report, about 800,000 individuals die due to suicide every year, that is 40 seconds per person. Suicide is a global problem and occurs throughout life. There are indications that for every adult suicide by suicide, there may have been more than 20 suicide attempts. (WHO, 2016)

Suicide is answerable for additional passing than intestinal sickness, bosom disease, war, or even manslaughter, as indicated by the WHO. It was the subsequent driving reason for death among 15-29-year-olds, guaranteeing 200,000 lives in 2016, bested distinctly by street injury.

The report discharged a day before World Suicide Prevention Day pegged India's self-destruction rate at 16.5 suicides per 100,000 individuals. Sri Lanka stands second in the area with a self-destruction pace of 14.6 and Thailand (14.4) third. India likewise had the third-most elevated female self-destruction rate (14.7) on the planet after Lesotho (24.4) and the Republic of Korea (15.4). All the data pertains to the WHO estimates for 2016. (Gupta, 2019).

Stages of suicide

According to Webb and Myfanwy the stages of suicide help to understand how a person falls short of expectations and desires which leads a person towards negative thoughts and self-destruction. The following are the experience indicators of pre-suicide stages mentioned by Webb and Myfanwy in their study.

1. Expectation crises.
2. Self attributions.
3. Excess of Self Awareness.
4. False Affect.
5. Cognitive Distructivism.
6. Disinhibition. (Webb & Myfanwy, 2019)

Psychosocial Risk Factors behind Suicide

According to Black, Warrack, and Winokur the disorder including, alcohol and drug abuse, is the most evident risk factor for suicide. (Black, Warrack, & Winokur, 1985).

Several Psychosocial factors leading to suicide ideation are briefly explained as follows:

1. **Environmental influence** – The trauma which is created in the environment due to suicide and chronic deaths after some of the other mental stressors leads to environmental influence for another person to do the same for their minimal stress situation. (KA & DP, 1982)
2. **Abuse** - The abuse here is indicating physical and sexual abuse as well as substance abuse which is followed by loss of expectations and desires. Sexual abuse, in particular, has received the most attention. (C, M, & L, 1994).
3. **Loss** – People faced the loss of either their close ones or the ones whom they are dependent on for their security needs and physiological needs. Since the loss can be in the sense of emotional dependency as well as financial dependency. (Botsis, Plutchik, Kotler, & van, 1995)
4. **Family Factor** –According to a study, the lack of communication or thought and feeling exchange between child and their parents becomes a risk factor. (MS, P, M, M, & D, 1996)

Other factors like ignorance, negligence, domestic violence, and poor parent-child relationships were correlated with adolescent psychopathology but did not have a strong role in suicide. (Kim, 2002)

5. **Stressful life events** - The loss of a loved one, failure in achieving the goals, illiteracy, dependency, and affection are life events that become negative among people who suicide. (CR, GL, SW, T, JR, & CA, 1993).
6. **Facilitating factors** - Poor social integration and social rehabilitation before the commencement of a suicide attempt is one of the most dangerous aspects of recurrence of suicide treatment. (CR, GL, SW, T, JR, & CA, 1993). Poor social adjustment correlates with suicidal behavior in adolescents. (Jacobsen, Rabinowitz, Popper, Solomon, Sokol, & Pfeffer, 1994). The immature coping technique like impulsivity or catastrophizing will lead to suicidal ideation. (DA, 1997)
7. **Social integration** - Looking into the vague aspect of suicide ideation, Durkheim explained that suicide can be initiated through the absence of cohesiveness and individual links. (Saunderson, Haynes, & Langford, 1998)

Different kinds of factors can combine to motivate a person to generate suicidal behavior. For example, when an individual develops a disorder or is high on mood swings leading to suicidal ideation. (Lee & Jung, 2006).

Buddhism

Buddhism has been viewed as the national religion of Thailand from the days of yore. Instead, Buddhism has been started in India by Siddhartha Gautama who was born between 566 and 480 BCE

in the land of Nepal (an old part of Indian territory). The word Buddha refers to “awakened one” which also means enlightenment. Gautam Buddha was prophesied that he will become a king if he will stay at home or a sage and the savior of humanity if he left, so he choose to leave the home for the sake of humanity. His father and family did not want him to leave the home because he wanted his son to be a king. Siddhartha grew up surrounded by luxury and riches but he became restless in his life of luxury. He went to travel and see the outside world and while doing so he observed 4 sights that left a long-lasting impression on him. He observed an old man, a very ill person, a funeral aside from a river, and a traveling monk (who has given up all pleasure of the flesh). He learned some simple truths of life that we all will grow old fall sick and die. So he decided to leave his previous life and devote himself to work and find a way to end suffering. (Chandra, 2000)

Principles of Buddhism in Suicide prevention

From the author’s viewpoint, the following areas can be approached for the prevention of the suicide ideation using the Buddhism principle:

- 1) Buddhism aspects toward suicide
- 2) The suffering of suicide
- 3) Detachment from Clinging
- 4) Four noble truths
- 5) Eightfold path in the prevention of Suicide
- 6) Role of concentration in the abandonment of Suicidal thoughts
- 7) The practice of meditation and mindfulness

1. Buddhist towards suicide - Monastic discipline (Vinaya) says that for any reason or cause a monk should not attempt suicide and should not let others suicide as well. (E P. , 1988). Motivation for suicide is generated by a particular craving for non-existence or destruction, cravings (Vibhava-tāccha). Self-destruction is just the result of the craving to demolish oneself (Narada, 1979).

2. The suffering in suicide – As mentioned earlier, there are many psychological as well as sociological factors behind suicide ideation. "Dukkha", means enduring, agony, distress, or wretchedness in the Pali language. The term Dukkha in the First Noble truth (W, 1974). The idea is explained from three different aspects: 1) As conventional misery (Dukkha), 2) As created by change (Vipariṇāmadukkha), and 3) As adapted states (Sāukh Aradukkha). (Mahathera, 1988).

Everything in the world will change at its speed whereas no situation or feeling in life is permanent or everlasting. The situations or feelings change sooner or later but it always changes with time. When it changes, it leaves a person in pain, suffering, unhappiness, and even suicide. This is suffering as it is produced by a change or a perpetual nature of existence. In this way, everything is dependent upon the three general attributes, in particular, temporariness (Anicca), misery (Dukkha), and egolessness (Anatta) Strictly, self-destruction is identified with the three parts of enduring as referenced. (Disayavanish & Disayavanish, J Med Assoc Thai 2007).

3. Detachment from Clinging - The mind tends to desire and cling to certain emotions, ideas, beliefs, expectations, ideas, cultures, personal images, and examples of reality.

A perfect self causes dukkha as a result of some sticking, for example, to the craving or conviction that there ought to be no inconsistency. A potential reason for an emotional meltdown is sticking to an unreasonable picture of how one's life ought to be sooner or later, in any event, when sensibly one has a decent life. (Disayavanish & Disayavanish, J Med Assoc Thai 2007)

Clinically, it is basic for individuals to stick to some personal conduct standards in any event, when they are not functioning admirably, now and again because the individuals characterize themselves as far as these practices and stick to those mental self-portraits. Sticking outcomes in mental impacts, protection from change, in any event, when the change would make the individual's life increasingly viable and more joyful. (Mikulas, 2004).

Dukkha and protection can be prevented from sticking and may likewise create mutilation in observations and weakness in speculation. This relates to sticking to the elements of numerous mental hypotheses, for example, psychodynamic barrier components, psychological cacophony hypothesis, the "new look" in recognition, and compositions in intellectual brain science.

Glasser (1976) told about some positive addictions like thinking and running; this is contested in Buddhist brain research. Jogging every possible morning can lead to ruin the suicide ideation and is also good for biological health and perhaps psychological health.

4. Four noble truths – These are for those seeking enlightenment and refuge from suffering. In brief, they are:

- (1) Suffering exists.
- (2) Suffering arises from attachment to desires.
- (3) Suffering ends when adversity becomes alone.
- (4) Freedom from suffering is conceivable by rehearsing the Eightfold Path.

The First Noble Truth is dukkha (suffering). The second truth is craving (which leads to clinging). The third truth is the need stops.

This was also concluded that Buddhist brain science is very much more humanistic than Freudian. It involves getting liberated from pollution, for example, the three toxic substances of the psyche, recognized as outrage, avarice, and dream. The fourth Noble Truth is the best approach to get liberated from longing for and contamination, the Eightfold Path (Das, 1997).

5. Eightfold Path in the prevention of Suicide - The Eightfold Path is expressed as the road to the cessation of suffering and enlightenment for personal happiness and the happiness of all others.

They are:

- (1) Right View/Right Understanding,
- (2) Right Thought/Intention,
- (3) Right Speech,
- (4) Right Action,
- (5) Right Livelihood,
- (6) Right Effort,

(7) Right Mindfulness, and

(8) Right Concentration

Right Faith (Samyak Drishti), Right Resolve (Samyak Sankalpa), Right Speech (Samyak Vakya), Right Action (Samyak Karmanta), Right Living (Samyak Ajiva), Right Thought (Samyak Smriti), Right Concentration (Samyak Samadhi), Right Effort (Samyak Vyayama).

The method is usually divided by Buddhist practitioners into three categories –

1. Wisdom - the wisdom (Panna) section comprises of right understanding and right intention.
2. Morality - the morality (sila) section comprising right speech, right action, and right livelihood.
3. Mental - the mental development section consists of the right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration.

The three sections are considered reciprocally and mutually supportive, such that Right View and Right Intent provide the initial intellectual reflections that support and motivate the experiential practices of mindfulness, morality, and concentration, cultivating the application of wisdom to all action, thereby facilitating “Right” (i.e. wholesome and skillful) pursuit of well-being (Bodhi, 1984).

6. Role of concentration in the abandonment of Suicidal thoughts – the learned focus of one’s attention is called concentration and it keeps one’s awareness on a specific arrangement of the substance of the psyche.

In Western psychology, fixation is for the most part observed as one part of the consideration, once in a while talked about as far as engaged consideration, controlled consideration, continued consideration, or watchfulness. (Moray, 1969)

William James gave the concept of fixation and a "training to improve the workforce which would be the instruction second to none." (1890, Buddhism)

One of the clearest possible uses of fixation preparation is in considering issues, including ADD/ADHD, a lack of ability to concentrate consistently clutter, ADD/ADHD is typically treated with drugs and may be joined with conduct alteration for hyperactivity.

If an individual sits discreetly and rehearses a focus type of reflection, at that point the psyche gets without a care in the world, which regularly loosens up the body. Focus delivered unwinding can be a viable treatment for anxiety. (DelMonte, 1985).

7. The practice of meditation and mindfulness – Mindfulness is defined as the highly active breadth and clarity of awareness and self-realization. It is the conduct that makes a person move and hon the point of mindfulness in the field of mental awareness.

In the most recent decade, mindfulness has gotten exceptionally well known in Western ways to deal with therapy, including psychotherapy (Boorstein, 1997; Germer, Siegel, and Fulton, 2005; Horowitz, 2002; Segall, 2005)

The Buddha and his devotees rehearsed and suggested mindfulness for pain control (de Silva, 1996).

At the University of Massachusetts, the late Jon Kabat-Zinn made a stress-reduction center to treat stress and pain. More than 16,000 clinical patients have experienced this program, presently called "mindfulness-based stress reduction". Treatment segments incorporate mindfulness contemplation and schoolwork tasks, careful yoga rehearses, body filters (gradually clearing consideration through the

body seeing sensations), the consciousness of breathing and stress, seeing sensations and musings non-disastrously, creating focus, correspondence preparing, and conversation of stress and adapting.

Discussion

By cutting off the cause of suffering one can prevent himself/herself from suicide ideation yet the four noble truths are rigid and are sure shot to be happening but after applying several Buddhism principles (like the Eightfold path, detachment from Clinging, concentration, mindfulness, and Meditation) in our lives, we can surely think rationally and work effectively to achieve a happy, satisfactory and anxiety-free lifespan. The creative forces behind every aspect of Buddhism are also reflected by Buddhism principles which encourage one to defeat his negative thoughts of self-destruction.

The Eightfold Path is communicated as the ways to the suspension of torment and edification for individual bliss and the satisfaction of all others. The Eightfold Path can work wisely in suicide prevention and blesses a person with wisdom (which is achieved by right understanding and right intention), morality (which is achieved by right speech, right action, and right livelihood), and mental development (which is achieved by right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration). By following these concepts one can easily defeat suicide ideation and succeed in their life.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

- There are no conflicts of interest to declare
- There is no involvement of human participants or/and animals.
- No informed consent was needed.

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